

Generalized scattering matrix for metallic nanorods

M.A. Kuntman, T. Çakır and E. Kuntman

We define a scattering matrix for metallic nanorods with arbitrary orientation, excitation and scattering directions

Orientation of the metallic nanorod in the space is determined by two angles, Θ and Φ (Fig.1). Scattering direction is given by angles α and β . Particle is illuminated by a completely polarized plane wave that propagates in the z -axis. Unit vectors $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ ($\hat{\mathbf{x}}'$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}'$) span the input (output) space for the scattering matrix. Horizontal and vertical excitation polarization states are applied separately and projections of the scattered far fields on the $\hat{\mathbf{x}}'$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}'$ basis are calculated for each case.

Figure 1: \mathbf{P} vector represents the nanorod. Incident plane wave ($\hat{\mathbf{k}}$) propagates in the z -axis. Horizontal and vertical excitation polarization states are applied separately. Unit vectors $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ ($\hat{\mathbf{x}}'$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}'$) span the input (output) space for the scattering matrix.

\mathbf{P} vector represents the nanorod (Fig.1):

$$\mathbf{P} = (-\cos \Phi \sin \Theta, \sin \Phi, \cos \Phi \cos \Theta) \quad (1)$$

$\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ vector defines the scattering direction:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}} = (\cos \beta \sin \alpha, \sin \beta, \cos \beta \cos \alpha) \quad (2)$$

$\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}$ define a right handed coordinate system for the input plane wave and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}', \hat{\mathbf{y}}', \hat{\mathbf{s}}$ define a right handed coordinate system for the scattered light:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}' = (\cos \alpha, 0, -\sin \alpha) \quad (3)$$

$\hat{\mathbf{y}}'$ is defined by the following cross product:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}' = \hat{\mathbf{s}} \otimes \hat{\mathbf{x}}' \quad (4)$$

Input (excitation) parameters P_x , P_y and output (scattering) parameters $P_{x'}$, $P_{y'}$ are defined by the following projections:

$$P_x = \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \quad P_y = \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}} \quad (5)$$

and

$$P_{x'} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}', \quad P_{y'} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}}' \quad (6)$$

Then the scattering matrix (Jones matrix) of the nanorod is

$$\mathbf{J} = \rho \begin{pmatrix} P_{x'} P_x & P_{x'} P_y \\ P_{y'} P_x & P_{y'} P_y \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where ρ is a combination of the far field factor and the Lorentzian polarizability. Apart from ρ , \mathbf{J} is a real matrix. It is worth to note that, in general, \mathbf{J} is not a symmetric Jones matrix, meaning that it may manifest circular polarization effects. But, since (apart from ρ) \mathbf{J} is a real matrix CD (circular dichroism) response is zero. Only for scattering in the $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ direction (forward scattering) \mathbf{J} is a symmetric matrix (no circular polarization effects). We note that \mathbf{J} can be written as a product of two matrices (input and output matrices):

$$\mathbf{J} = \rho \begin{pmatrix} 0 & P_{x'} \\ 0 & P_{y'} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ P_x & P_y \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

We also calculate the components of the scattered far fields:

$$E_i^x = \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}} [\mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}' (\hat{\mathbf{x}}')_i + \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}}' (\hat{\mathbf{y}}')_i] \quad (9)$$

where $i = x, y, z$ and the superscript denotes horizontal excitation polarization state of light. Similarly, for vertical polarization excitation

$$E_i^y = \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}} [\mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}' (\hat{\mathbf{x}}')_i + \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}}' (\hat{\mathbf{y}}')_i] \quad (10)$$

We may define a scattered far field vector \mathbf{E} for each excitation polarization:

$$\mathbf{E}^j = (E_x^j, E_y^j, E_z^j). \quad (11)$$

where j stands for x, y . The elements of the Jones matrix can be retrieved as projections of the \mathbf{E} vector on the $\hat{\mathbf{x}}'$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}'$ basis:

$$J_{11} = \rho P_{x'} P_x = \rho \mathbf{E}^x \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}' \quad (12)$$

$$J_{12} = \rho P_{x'} P_y = \rho \mathbf{E}^y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}' \quad (13)$$

$$J_{21} = \rho P_{y'} P_x = \rho \mathbf{E}^x \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}}' \quad (14)$$

$$J_{22} = \rho P_{y'} P_y = \rho \mathbf{E}^y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}}' \quad (15)$$